

CHANGES IN LANGUAGE DUE TO NEW PHYSICS

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The purpose of this article is to show the expansion of language with the development of science. New theories introduced into physics caused very serious problems. Especially the so-called "new physics" of relativity and quantum theories forced us to search for a suitable scientific language to keep pace with the scientific reality that opened before us. The new physics damaged the deterministic mechanism. The scheme also changed the perception of language used by the scientific community. This situation, not only scientists, but also many people who use this language, felt the need to change the everyday language they use to describe scientific reality. In other words, this situation changed the types and fields of concepts used in physics along with the new physics.

Key words: Classical physics, modern physics, language of science

"Words are needed only when there is no desire; where there is no loss, there is no language."

Jacques Lacan

Enter

Until the 20th century, the development of physics in terms of precision was emphasized by expressing much of physics in everyday language. Thus physical facts requiring proof could be realized by a small number of mechanical rules. Newtonian physics, which dominated until the beginning of the 20th century, is one of the most important arguments in the history of physics. The motion of massive bodies such as the Sun, planets, and stars could be easily predicted using this physics. Newton's physics, almost divine in this sense, has taken its place in the history of science as the first and most mature example of scientific research that can explain the phenomenon of motion in everyday language that is still used today. earth and sky.²⁰ One might think that before the 11th century, Newton's physics was admired, perhaps because he was the son of a farmer, or because he wrote about three million words on religion and religious history. Of course, it can also be said that his writings in both science and alchemy were essentially religiously motivated, which undeniably created a large fan base well into the 20th century.

The dominant language until the 20th century, especially with the "mathematical principles of natural philosophy", painted a completely new picture of the universe and paved the way for the hypothetical deductive universe, a new method in philosophy and science. Therefore, the language of this century had a close influence on this century and its people, not only in terms of science, but also in terms of methodology. One of the most important features of this century is the dominance of deterministic-mechanistic language. Because, according to Newton's cupidic paradigm, science and everything was moving from effect to cause. The language used in this view was so powerful that it can still be seen in many philosophers and scientists today. In conclusion, hearing language from Newton's Principia to the 20th century was one of the stages in the evolutionary process of scientific language. In the 19th century, new ideas and discoveries in natural sciences brought new scientific debates to the agenda, emphasizing the inadequacy of the scientific language of the past period and declaring that concepts such as force, mass, speed, energy, and momentum may lose their validity. only affects the large mass.

He assessed 19th century physics as a failure from the point of view of scientific language. In the 19th century, the language of science developed rapidly, created the ground for the emergence of new ideas and publications, and revealed that science is not the pursuit of rich amateurs. 19. No matter how much the new scientific language that appeared in the 19th century developed, it did not achieve the intended effect. The Newtonian paradigm is so deeply entrenched that Isaac Newton's laws of motion and gravitation are nearly 100 years old when Antoine Lavoisier demonstrates the conservation of matter through his quantitative chemistry experiments in 1780. Newton offered us the scientific language we need to understand all of nature. But the limits are still worth pushing. People were interested in learning the proper scientific language of matter, light, heat, electricity, and magnetism. So much so that this state of affairs continued until the new physics known as relativity and quantum theory was explained.

New physics

At the beginning of the 20th century, quantum physics founded by Max Planck's quantum theory, special and general relativity theory advanced by A. Einstein began to replace Newtonian physics. The new physics began after the Newtonian paradigm was replaced by two major revolutions in physics. By adding the dimension of time to the three-dimensional fabric of space, special relativity spoke of a new four-dimensional space-time continuum. According to

this theory, time cannot easily be claimed to be universal and continuous. Any observed event is perceived by two different observers moving at different speeds at different times. Therefore, while one observer may perceive the same events as occurring at the same time, another observer perceives the same events as occurring at a different time.

These strange circumstances naturally changed the view of space and time and the belief in its absoluteness. This change in space-time concepts naturally led to a change in the language of concepts used to explain nature. The language used by the theory of quantum and relativity, which constitutes the new physics, changed the views of physicists on reality and caused a radical change in the concepts of space-time, matter, and cause and effect. This emerging new language is described by terms such as organic, holistic, and ecological, and instead of understanding the indivisible, indivisible wholeness that prevailed in the Newtonian paradigm, language that is divisive and even transformable is on the agenda. brought Within this variability, especially the transformation of the dual form of matter (wave/particle) into energy and its evolution from a 2-3 dimensional space-time texture to a 4-5-dimensional space-time can be cited as an example.

Although changes in language with new physics have opened new doors to describe the universe and its equations, even today we see that it does not achieve the desired effect. So much so that today's physicists still try to explain quantum and relativity theories in Newtonian language, which is one of the best examples of this state of affairs. The new language of physics created a wave of reaction that spread and knocked on everyone's door. natural sciences. This situation caused the language of science to slip from under the feet of supporters of new physics. In particular, the deterministic-mechanistic language used in the expression of scientific processes was harmed, and physicists realized that experimental results based on cause-effect relationships do not create a happy picture. Furthermore, the fact that the language needed to describe the phenomena arising from the new language was not given to non-physicists also showed that the language of physics derived from the Newtonian paradigm was not the ultimate language for confronting the unknown.

With the new physics, changes in language created a criterion for explaining and describing experimental results and created a number of problems in terms of the level of understanding of the relevant topic or topics. These problems left us with the questions of how to define the results and how

far their limits should be extended, especially if the results obtained from experiments are expressed in deterministic-mechanistic language.

Language in general and scientific terms

Language is a natural means of understanding between people. According to Wittgenstein, language is a part of our organism and is no less complex. In Foucault, language shows itself differently. In other words, Foucault emphasizes that language appears first of all in its raw and primitive existence as a simple and material form of writing, a trace on things, a sign written on the world and constituting one of its most indelible images. Noting that he does not have accurate information about the formation of the language, O'ner emphasizes that the language as a means of conveying the meaning of the concepts encountered in everyday life includes many concepts. Because these concepts have been used by mankind for years, we think we know what they mean. Foucault argues that language is one of the three levels of language, that the conceptual layer of language is unique and absolute in a certain sense, and that this layer creates the two forms of speech that surround it.

These forms of speech; These are texts in which the interpretation revises the signs given above in a new speech form, and the following interpretation includes the primacy of signs that are visible to everyone. For example, we can say a piece of wood or tin. However, if we consider the texts as a whole, we will see that they cannot be called a piece of water. Because, according to the hidden primary texts, the word men cannot be used for liquid things. This ambiguity in the meanings of words led to the appearance of a new, hitherto unknown problem. Until the 17th century, it was asked what the word meant. From the 17th century, the question began to be asked how to communicate what this sign means. While the classical period answered such questions through representational solutions, the modern period responded by taking into account the meaning and the strategy of giving meaning. . Ambiguity in the meanings of words appeared as a situation of assigning different meanings to words, violating the deep interconnectedness of the world and language.

Heisenberg expresses this situation as follows: "The ability to implement the definitions we have made with the help of other definitions has forced us to rely only on a few basic concepts whose existence has taken refuge." The problem of the concept of language is also found in ancient Greek philosophy. An attempt has been made to look at this situation from a philosophical point of view, taking into account the connection between being and thinking, words and meaning. A word is not a symbol, a sign, or an indicator of being, but is a real

part of it; language was seen as the external covering and basis of knowledge. Plato believed that objective truth cannot be reached by words. "Thinking" had to be based only on itself and open to its true objects, that is, its ideas. Discussing the correctness of the names given to objects in the Cratylus dialogue, Plato says: "When I speak, I communicate through something which is not like what I think. For there is an analogy between what you call Sklêrotês and l (ribbon) no". In Plato's philosophy, the word and the object are connected in such a way that the word represents the thing (object) in thought. However, according to Plato, who thought that thinking should be based only on itself and open to its real objects, the word is not a necessary element for thinking. Aristotle discussed the rules and stages of acquiring scientific knowledge and revealed whether scientific knowledge is possible or not.

In other words, he tried to understand how apodeictic knowledge occurs in any discipline. In addition, he revealed the scientific structure of the conclusions we make by solving the forms used in language and solving their consequences. Aristotle's analysis of language led to the establishment of a certain order of expression in our way of thinking. Clarity of language by revealing the first science of logic known as Aristotelian logic.

Natural sciences and language

Wittgenstein said that "facts are the whole world" and proposed to consider all sentences as a language in order to analyze the structure of the world. The use of language as a means of communication in the natural sciences, in a sense, supports Wittgenstein's words. In particular, words and their different meanings reveal different linguistic processes created by facts. Different language processes make logical inferences more important, especially in scientific matters. In this sense, unequivocal expressions, which are biased by logic, are not healthy and cause many problems. This creates significant difficulties, especially between particulars and universals. It is well known that the desire to derive the universal from the particular is a common reflex in the natural sciences.

In other words, he evaluates individual events as the cause of simple and general laws. If these separate phenomena are to be expressed by the concept of language, then it seems that they are reduced to several concepts. According to Cassirer, the only, that is, the only and limited existence is understood. isolate and explain everything else related to existence. In this sense, separate phenomena and many concepts related to them must be redefined. So much so that instead of creating these phenomena only qualitatively and without any

precision, it is necessary to describe them one by one and with great precision, down to the smallest details. An attempt to define individual phenomena and their specific concepts in everyday language. the one we are using is similar to the error we are experiencing now. We can say that, especially in everyday language, individual events and concepts cannot be obtained by drawing logical conclusions from general laws.

Sample natural phenomena and the new language of physics

The theories of special and general relativity and quantum theory, two of the most surprising revolutions of the last century, created serious cracks in the natural sciences. The first of these cracks appeared with the theories of relativity, and in particular, the theory of special relativity led to the emergence of speculative ideas about positionally related relations between phenomena. According to Bertrand Russell, the theory of relativity, which was absolute until the classical definitions but independent of positions, made the understanding of the classical perspective stronger in 20th century physics research than that defined by Newton. In this sense, Kant's independent ontological structures, such as absolute space and absolute time, were nothing more than a priori necessity underlying external perceptions. The theories of relativity undermined Kant's idea that we could gain inductive knowledge of the laws of nature and foregrounded Humean's skeptical objection. This skeptic challenge changed the perspective on the concepts of space and time, revealing what language needed to be used to redefine these concepts as problems to be solved.

Theories of relativity and language

1905 has a special place among the miraculous years in the history of science. In 1905, Einstein published five extraordinary studies. All these are important in themselves. However, two of these studies changed the face of physics. In particular, special relativity is closely related to ancient physics in its epistemological assessments of velocities being very small compared to the speed of light, and the works of leading physicists of the past as well as of our own age. It can be discussed together with the intellectual direction of the research being conducted. The theories of relativity are mathematical symbols from their origin. It helps to explain how to interpret the results obtained from the experiments and prepared a suitable basis for expressing the results in everyday language.

In particular, the fact that Lorentz transformations, which represent the shortening of the length of bodies, were known and used much earlier seemed to be a favorable opportunity for the language derived from relativity theories to

be expressed in everyday language. If a special theory, the theory of relativity had to be expressed in everyday language, the words that make up the theory and their meanings do not appear to be contradictory. In other words, when special relativity is interpreted in everyday language, it is concluded that this theory can be easily applied to every field where the concept of relativity is applied. Therefore, whether the Lorentz contraction in the lengths of objects closely related to this theory is real or an illusion, or the meaning of the word synchronicity, depends more on concepts than on facts. 'looks.

Quantum theory and language

The term quantum, which refers to the fact that energy exists in finite packets and cannot be divided into infinitely small ones, was coined in the 1900s to explain the perplexing problems of how light is emitted and absorbed in a remote corner of physics. Two quantum revolutions followed this movement. The first is the period between 1900-1925, when scientists discussed and developed this theory without attracting public attention, and the second is the period between 1925-1927, when the strange results of this theory aroused interest in society. became a topic of discussion and called it quantum mechanics. Even today, more than eighty years later, humanity does not know what to do with this second quantum revolution, which is amazing, fantastic and even shocking.

In particular, the absence of any guide to match the concepts of ordinary language to the mathematical symbols of the second quantum revolution revealed a serious pessimism in understanding this revolution in terms of the use of language. With the second quantum revolution, called quantum mechanics. It was seen that the atom and its concepts cannot be explained in ordinary language. Although it was clear that with the second quantum revolution we had to get rid of everyday language, this revolution could also see the formalistic and axiomatic approach of mathematics. Thus, it seemed that there was no other way than to explain the mathematical scheme of quantum mechanics at the atomic scale with classical mechanics. However, unlike the classical statistical theory, "probability experiments" appear only in quantum situations, and we encounter quantum-theoretical solutions, the solutions of which do not resemble the solutions in the field of classical physics, only on a larger scale. It required us to carefully approach the concept of a classic solution.

The lack of alliance between quantum language and everyday language can be described as revolutionary language problems. The fact that people were deprived of the right to speak clearly, especially in terms of understanding or

describing the atom, made them ask themselves some questions about this revolution. Among these questions, we see that we are particularly faced with questions about the discourse of physicists after the quantum revolution and the scientific language that corresponds to the logical structure of the quantum revolution.

Summary

In the last century, many new concepts entered physics. These new concepts, while creating an atmosphere of chaos, also bring many important results that surprise people. In other words, concepts played a leading role in the construction of physics, which was later called "new physics". In this new physics, especially the concept of the electromagnetic field, Maxwell's facts, relativity and quantum theorems allowed physicists to ask themselves whether we should use everyday language. Although the phenomena of new physics necessitated the use of a suitable language, this language was used by many physicists much later.

Because the emergence of these concepts depends on changes in our deep-rooted designs in science, and such radical changes did not happen so easily and suddenly. The field of application of new concepts arising from new physics is not only physical created the field of application of knowledge, that is, new concepts arising from the science of physics. an extensive, consistent, and closed system, but also created a language that was used not only by physicists, but also by technicians to engineers. The transition from a deterministic-mechanistic understanding of the universe to a deterministic model of the universe has always appeared as an extension of this language. In particular, the assumption that the sequence of events in time is independent of the way they are located in the space-time cycle is always accepted among the designs of this new physics. In addition, the results of this language include the evolution from Euclidean space to Mikovsky space and the transition to Riemannian geometry. The greatest antinomy created by the language discovered by the new physics was revealed by quantum theory. In particular, the fact that the observation process has a certain effect on the observed phenomenon has become a part of the overall concept. This language further increased the distinction between the observer and the observed language by saying that the observer and the observed should be considered as a whole. The integral relationship between the observed and the observer showed that the language emerging from the new physics was a necessary condition for the realization of the ideal of objectivity, which was considered the basis of all sciences.

As a result, language is derived from language. the new physics, if it is based on facts, that is, on experimental results, can be used in everyday language, freed from the axiomatic and symbolic difficulties imposed by logical principles.

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